

Synthesis and spectral studies of Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 17-membered N₂O₃ macrocycles

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Abstract : 1+1 Cyclocondensation of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane with α -diketones such as benzil and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil in the presence of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺ and Ba²⁺ ions as templates yields a series of complexes of the type [MLX]X (where M = Mg^{II}, X = Cl; M = Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II}, X = NCS; L = N₂O₃ type macrocycle having 17-membered ring). The resulting complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductance measurements, IR, ¹H NMR and FAB mass spectral studies.

Keywords : Macrocylic complexes, alkaline earth metals, IR spectra, ¹H NMR spectra, FAB mass spectra.

Introduction

The field of macrocyclic complexes is developing very fast due to their resemblance to many naturally occurring molecules, such as metalloproteins, porphyrins and cobalamines¹. The macrocycles have various applications in bioinorganic chemistry, material science, catalysis, separation and encapsulation processes, hydrometallurgy, formation of compounds with unusual properties, metal-metal interactions, transport and activation of small molecules²⁻⁷. Macrocycles with mixed oxygen-nitrogen donor set can be used as sensors for cations and anions and as molecular scaffolds for materials and as biological models⁸⁻¹². In competitive extraction and transport of transition and post transition metal ions the mixed-donor cyclic and acyclic macrocyclic ligands are used as ionophores¹³⁻¹⁶. N₂O₂ and N₂O₃ donor type ligands have also been examined extensively as potential transition metal ion selective reagents. Earlier, a series of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of N₂O₂¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of N₂O₃²⁰ macrocycles have been synthesized in our laboratories. In the present paper alkaline earth metal complexes of 17-membered N₂O₃ macrocycles derived from α -diketones such as benzil and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane have been described.

Experimental

MgCl₂.6H₂O (Himedia), CaCl₂.2H₂O (Merck), SrCl₂.6H₂O (Merck) and BaCl₂.2H₂O (Merck) used were of AR grade. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (Merck), benzil (Aldrich) and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil (Fluka) were used as such and *n*-butanol and methanol were distilled before use. Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically by EDTA using Eriochrome Black T as indicator and barium was determined gravimetrically as BaSO₄²¹. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Shimadzu-8400 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ on a JEOL AL-300 Spectrometer. Conductances in DMSO were determined using Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-304. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 Mass Spectrometer/Datasystem using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes :

(a) *Synthesis of Mg^{II} complexes of 17-membered N₂O₃ macrocycles :*

To a butanolic solution of MgCl₂.6H₂O (975 mg, 4.79 mmol in 10 ml *n*-butanol), a butanolic solution of benzil (1.00 g, 4.79 mmol, dissolved in 10 ml *n*-butanol by heating at 40 °C) was added. Then a butanolic solution of

1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (1.05 g, 4.79 mmol in 10 ml *n*-butanol) was added to this under continuous stirring. The contents were stirred for 6 h and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried *in vacuo*. Mg^{II} complex of 17-membered diazatrioxamacrocycle was isolated. Similar method was adopted for the synthesis of Mg^{II} complex of macrocycle derived from 4,4'-dimethylbenzil and 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane.

(b) *Synthesis of Ca^{II} complexes of 17-membered N₂O₃ macrocycles :*

To a butanolic solution of CaCl₂·2H₂O (885 mg, 6.01 mmol in 15 ml *n*-butanol), a butanolic solution of benzil (911 mg, 6.01 mmol, dissolved in 10 ml *n*-butanol by heating at 40 °C) was added. To this reaction mixture, a butanolic solution of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (1.34 g, 6.09 mmol in 10 ml *n*-butanol) was added under continuous stirring. As no solid appeared, a methanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (592 mg, 6.01 mmol in 10 ml methanol) was added. The contents were stirred for 8 h and the temperature was maintained at 70 °C throughout the course of the reaction. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under *vacuo*. Similarly, Ca^{II} complex of other oxazamacrocycle derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil was synthesized. The Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of oxazamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α-diketones such as benzil and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil were also synthesized by similar procedure.

Results and discussion

The reactions of metal chlorides with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α-diketones such as benzil and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios resulted in the formation of metal complexes of 17-membered N₂O₃ macrocycles (Fig. 1). The resulting complexes were obtained as white solids. On heating they do not melt but decompose. These are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and ether but soluble in DMSO. The analyses and characteristics of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The molar conductances of the complexes indicate their 1 : 1 electrolytic nature²². Thus one thiocyanato group is coordinated giving hexa-coordinated environment around the metal atom.

Fig. 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

Infrared spectra :

In the IR spectra of macrocyclic complexes, absence of absorption bands at 3200–3400 cm⁻¹ and ~1700 cm⁻¹ due to unreacted -NH₂ or C=O groups respectively, suggests complete condensation of the amino groups with the keto groups^{23,24}. All the complexes exhibit medium to strong intensity bands in the region 1580–1640 cm⁻¹ due to the coordinated $\nu(C=N)$ ^{25,26}. The absorption bands in the region 1430–1560 cm⁻¹ are due to C=C stretching of phenyl ring and C–H bending vibrations²⁷. All the complexes show bands in the region 420–460 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to $\nu(M-N)$ vibrations²⁸. N-Bonded thiocyanate stretching frequencies are observed at 2040–2070 cm⁻¹ in Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes. The lowering of these frequencies in these complexes as compared to that reported for free thiocyanate (2100 cm⁻¹) supports the coordination of the thiocyanate group to the metal atom through nitrogen atom. Fenton and Cook²⁹ reported N-bonded thiocyanate stretching frequencies at 2063, 2073 and 2081 cm⁻¹ in Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes respectively, of the macrocycle 3,15,21-triaza-6,9,12-trioxabicyclo(15.3.1)heneicosa-1(21),2,5,17,19-pentene.

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of the macrocyclic complexes

Sl. no.	Complexes	Colour and decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) : Found/(Calcd.)		Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
				Metal	N	
1.	[MgL ¹ Cl]Cl	White (179)	31	4.89 (4.97)	5.67 (5.72)	60
2.	[MgL ² Cl]Cl	White (198)	29	4.64 (4.70)	5.37 (5.41)	71
3.	[CaL ¹ NCS]NCS	White (210)	24	7.21 (7.27)	5.03 (5.09)	64
4.	[CaL ² NCS]NCS	White (198)	28	6.85 (7.09)	4.72 (4.83)	78
5.	[SrL ¹ NCS]NCS	White (211)	35	14.61 (14.66)	4.62 (4.68)	59
6.	[SrL ² NCS]NCS	White (188)	21	13.93 (14.00)	4.38 (4.47)	63
7.	[BaL ¹]NCS	White (212)	27	21.14 (21.21)	4.27 (4.32)	77
8.	[BaL ² NCS]NCS	White (205)	24	20.29 (20.33)	4.10 (4.14)	70

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectrum of Mg^{II} complex [Mg{(C₆H₅)₂[17]-dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl has been recorded in DMSO-*d*₆. A peak at δ 2.49 ppm is observed in the spectrum due to the residual methyl protons of the solvent DMSO-*d*₆. Free diamine shows a peak at δ 1.43 ppm due to -NH₂ protons which disappears in the spectrum of macrocyclic complex confirming the condensation of -NH₂ groups of the amine residue with the C=O groups of the ketone residue to give macrocycles having C=N linkages. In the spectrum of macrocyclic complex the -NCH₂ (α) and -OCH₂ protons merge together and a peak is observed at δ 2.76 ppm. The β -CH₂ protons of the amine residue appear at δ 1.80 ppm. In 1,2,8,9-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione (KIM, Fig. 2) the α -CH₂ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.63 ppm and β -CH₂ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm. The free macrocycles have not been isolated during the present investigations but they are expected to exhibit the -NCH₂ (α) and β -CH₂ protons almost at the same positions as reported for KIM. As compared to KIM, in macrocyclic complex, the peaks due to -NCH₂ (α) and β -CH₂ protons are observed at higher field. This high-field shift of these protons confirms the coordination of the nitrogen and oxygen atoms of the macrocycle to the metal atom.

Fig. 2. KIM.

In free benzil [C₆H₅^aCOCOC₆H₅^a], the C₆H₅^a protons exhibit a peak at δ 7.56 ppm. In the complex, C₆H₅^a protons of the ketone moiety appear at δ 7.24 ppm.

FAB mass spectra :

The FAB mass spectra of [Ca{(Ph)₂[17]dieneN₂O₃}NCS]NCS and [Ba{(Ph)₂[17]dieneN₂O₃}NCS]NCS have been recorded using 3-nitro benzyl alcohol matrix. Peaks at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to matrix. The spectra have been analyzed on the basis of isotopic abundances of different nuclei particularly those of Ca, Ba and S and only the most abundant isotopic peaks have been taken into consideration (Table 2). The complexes show peaks corresponding to molecular ions [M]⁺ and free macrocycle [L]⁺, which confirms the formation of the macrocyclic complexes. In the complexes the peaks due to [M+H]⁺ or [L+H]⁺ have also been observed. In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ions and the macrocycles, the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to vari-

Table 2. m/z Values and % relative intensities of important peaks in FAB mass spectra of Ca^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of macrocycles

Sl. no.	Fragment	Complex	
		$[\text{Ca}\{(\text{Ph})_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NCS}]\text{NCS}$	$\text{Ba}\{(\text{Ph})_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NCS}]\text{NCS}$
1.	$[\text{M}]^+$	550 (2.70)	648 (3.6)
2.	$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	551 (1.35)	649 (2.77)
3.	$[\text{M}-\text{NCS}]^+$	492 (2.70)	590 (1.38)
4.	$[\text{M}-2\text{NCS}]^+$	434 (5.40)	532 (2.77)
5.	$[\text{M}-2\text{NCS}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$	357 (5.40)	455 (5.55)
6.	$[\text{M}-2\text{NCS}-2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$	280 (1.35)	378 (1.38)
7.	$[\text{L}]^+$	394 (10.81)	394 (2.77)
8.	$[\text{L}+\text{H}]^+$	395 (1.35)	395 (7.08)
9.	$[\text{L}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$	317 (8.10)	317 (1.38)
10.	$[\text{L}-2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$	240 (4.72)	240 (1.38)

ous fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycle and its complexes. The fragmentation pattern for the complex $[\text{Ca}\{(\text{Ph})_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NCS}]\text{NCS}$ is given in Fig. 3. The complex exhibits molecular ion $[\text{M}]^+$ (a) peak at m/z 550 (2.70%) and $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ peak at m/z

551 (1.35%). Fragments **b** and **c** are formed due to the successive loss of two NCS groups from the molecular ion a and appear at m/z 492 (2.70%) and m/z 434 (5.40%) respectively. There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex :

Fig. 3. Fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Ca}\{(\text{Ph})_2[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NCS}]\text{NCS}$.

Note

Table 3. Calculations of relative abundances of molecular ion [M]⁺ (a) of complex [Ca{(Ph)₂[17]dieneN₂O₃}NCS]NCS due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion*

Sl. no.	Ion composition	<i>m/z</i>	Fractional abundance	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
1.	⁴⁰ Ca(C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₃ ³² S ₂)	550	(0.969)(0.95) ² = 0.874	0.874	100
2.	⁴⁰ Ca(C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₃ ³² S ³⁴ S)	552	(0.969)(0.95)(0.043) × 2 = 0.073	0.073	8.35
3.	⁴⁰ Ca(C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₃ ³⁴ S ₂)	554	(0.969)(0.043) ² = 0.001	0.019	2.17
4.	⁴⁴ Ca(C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₃ ³² S ₂)	554	(0.02)(0.95) ² = 0.018		
5.	⁴⁴ Ca(C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₃ ³² S ³⁴ S)	556	(0.02)(0.95)(0.043) × 2 = 0.001	0.001	0.11
6.	⁴⁴ Ca(C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₃ ³⁴ S ₂)	558	(0.02)(0.043) ² = 0.00003	0.00003	0.003

Table 4. Calculations of relative abundances of various fragments of the complex [Ca{(Ph)₂[17]dieneN₂O₃}NCS]NCS due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion*

Sl. no.	Ion composition	<i>m/z</i>	Fractional abundance	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
Fragment b : [Ca(C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₃ O ₃ S)]					
1.	⁴⁰ Ca(C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₃ O ₃ ³² S)	492	(0.969)(0.95) = 0.920	100	2.70
2.	⁴⁰ Ca(C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₃ O ₃ ³⁴ S)	494	(0.969)(0.043) = 0.038	4.13	0.11
3.	⁴⁴ Ca(C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₃ O ₃ ³² S)	496	(0.02)(0.95) = 0.019	2.06	0.05
4.	⁴⁴ Ca(C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₃ O ₃ ³⁴ S)	498	(0.02)(0.043) = 0.0008	0.086	0.0002
Fragment c : [Ca(C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₃ O ₃)]					
1.	⁴⁰ Ca(C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃)	434	(0.969)	100	5.40
2.	⁴⁴ Ca(C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃)	438	(0.020)	2.06	0.11
Fragment d : [Ca(C ₁₈ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₃)]					
1.	⁴⁰ Ca(C ₁₈ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₃)	357	(0.969)	100	5.40
2.	⁴⁴ Ca(C ₁₈ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₃)	361	(0.020)	2.06	0.11
Fragment e : [Ca(C ₁₈ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₃)]					
1.	⁴⁰ Ca(C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃)	280	(0.969)	100	1.35
2.	⁴⁴ Ca(C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃)	284	(0.020)	2.06	0.03

*(a_A.^xA + b_A.^yA + c_A.^zA + ...) ⁿ (a_B.^xB + b_B.^yB + c_B.^zB + ...) ^m where a_A, b_A, c_A etc. are the fractional abundances of the isotopes ^xA, ^yA, ^zA of element A and n is the number of atoms of A present in the ion; similarly for m atoms of B and so on.

Pathway [A] : In this pathway, the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and step by step loss of C₆H₅ groups from **c** gives peaks at *m/z* 357 (5.40%) and 280 (1.35%) due to the species **d** and **e** respectively. Loss of Ca from the species **e** finally gives the species **h**, *m/z* 240 (4.72%).

Pathway [B] : In this pathway, the metal ion may be lost from the macrocyclic complex in the beginning and a peak at *m/z* 394 (10.81%) appears due to the free macrocycle **f**. Step by step loss of two C₆H₅ groups from the macrocycle gives peak at *m/z* 317 (8.10%) and 240 (4.72%) due to the species **g** and **h** respectively. The spectrum of [Ca{(Ph)₂[17]dieneN₂O₃}NCS]NCS has been

analyzed on the basis of isotopic abundances of different nuclei particularly those of Ca{⁴⁰Ca (96.94%) and ⁴⁴Ca (2.08%)} and S {³²S (95.02%) and ³⁴S (4.21%)}. Various isotopic peaks have been observed but the most abundant peaks have been considered while discussing the fragmentation pattern, these isotopic peaks have been analyzed on the basis of theoretical calculations (Tables 3–4). The calculation for this complex (Table 3) shows the molecular ion isotopic peaks at *m/z* 550, 552, 554, 556 and 558 due to the different isotopes of Ca (⁴⁰Ca and ⁴⁴Ca) and S (³²S and ³⁴S) and their relative abundances are 2.70, 0.22, 0.05, 0.002 and 0.00008% respectively. The peaks at *m/z* 552, 554, 556 and 558 are neglected

due to their low abundances. Similar calculations for other fragments of this complex are given in Table 4. Thus the mass spectral studies strongly support the formation of macrocyclic complexes.

Conclusion

Thus the IR, ¹H NMR and FAB mass spectral data support the structures of the complexes.

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